

REACHING BEYOND ETHICS – PERSPECTIVES OF HUMAN RIGHTS EDUCATION ON AN OPEN SEARCH INDEX

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Abstract

In order for an open and free search index to be a lasting alternative to established digital infrastructures processes of digitalization need to be addressed in a way that includes their profound influence on the human condition. Within the field of education that means to didacticize digitalization not solely in terms of application and usage. In addition to a well-versed media use (including the use of search engines), it should be asked how digitalization processes affect people's relationships to themselves, to the world and their fellow human beings. It is only against this backdrop – which reaches beyond ethics – that allows for questions of 'wrong' and 'right' to be asked in a sensible manner in the first place. The insight into a fundamental (digital-) technological impact on the human being – which is captured in this paper mainly with concepts from cultural sciences (first and foremost with Felix Stalder's notion of digitality) – makes an educational process plausible which obtains its normative orientation from human rights education. Reasoning for this orientation offers a normative counterweight to possible problematic developments within the 'culture of digitality' (Stalder) – which will be illustrated in this paper conclusively with the example of politics.

THE 'FABRIC' OF CULTURE, SOCIETY AND HUMANESS IS CHANGING

The task to index, analyse and to make available content from the internet can be compared to the role of a librarian. There is, for example, the need to keep the inventory up to date, to structure the information in an appropriate manner and to supervise these processes with an eye for legal and moral boundaries [1]. However, there are limits to this analogy: While past librarians undoubtedly already dealt with a vast amount of information, this information was nevertheless restricted – especially in its production – to a certain group of people. There were (and still are) several gatekeepers whether it be within academia, publishing or institutions for distribution (like, for example, libraries) who rendered specific kinds of information more valuable than others and, accordingly, decided what is published (and in which way it is published and displayed for the public). Thus, what Marshall McLuhan called in the mid-20th century the Gutenberg-galaxy was – at least to some extent and especially during Early Modern Times – still overseable.

This changed drastically with digitalization: The amount of people contributing information of all sorts as well as the information itself increased immensely. The consequences of this development are ambivalent: On the one hand there is the possibility for more diversity due to the

disempowerment of former gatekeepers [2]; on the other hand, it is – today more than ever – impossible for a single person to navigate the available information without any help. With this task humans need assistance – which they get more and more from technology. What is interesting in this context is that some of the forerunners who helped to finance and push forward the required technical assistance positioned themselves quite clearly in opposition to the above-mentioned advantage of more diversity. As early as the 1990s Peter Thiel who later on became the co-founder of PayPal and an influential investor had objected multicultural ideals for society advocated by some students and lecturers at Stanford University [3]. Instead, he relied on technical progress together with capitalism. In an article from 2009 – which almost reads like a confession – Thiel predicted a deadly race between technics and politics; unmistakably, the outcome he hoped for was for political influence to vanish altogether. „The fate of our world may depend on the effort of a single person who builds or propagates the machinery of freedom that makes the world safe for capitalism” [4].

Confronting Thiel's position – which can be called a 'technicism' or a 'solutionism' [5] – with ethics leads to unequivocal results: There is no defending Thiel's stance without giving up basic principles of a democratic society characterized by inclusivity and equality. Therefore, it is not the obvious that is interesting about Thiel's point of view but what lies beneath his hope for the invention of what he calls a 'machinery of freedom' – which brings us back to the analogy between a search index and a library introduced at the very beginning. It is this very phrase that lets an expectation of salvation resonate within Thiel's text and that elucidates that we do not only have to deal with an ever-growing library, that is, with much more information and with new ways of gatekeeping but also that the library expanded (and still expands) in a way that is inseparably interwoven with human life and identity formation. Technology is not the 'other' we are confronted with but it is 'within us'; it shapes our way of thinking, our dreams and hopes, and our perception of the world as well as of each other – which eventually lets some of us draw the conclusion that freedom is something to be installed by machines. In short, the entire 'fabric' of society and what it means to be human has changed with digitalization (as both had changed in the past, for example when Johannes Gutenberg invented letterpress printing).

The development of a free and open search index has to keep this insight in mind while advancing. The (seemingly) more pressing questions of (e. g.) market power, transparency of algorithmic decision making or digital self-determination have to be accompanied by the basic notion that what we consider to be 'free' and 'open' has been changed

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by this very technology we are trying to apply these attributes to. In order to address, for instance, ethical questions in a satisfactory manner they have to be asked against the backdrop of an ever-changing *conditio humana* which prevents them from being abstract considerations about ‘right’ and ‘wrong’. This perspective – reaching beyond ethics – is important even for the most free and open search index or the most transparent algorithms because it raises awareness for the question what qualities of being human are not sufficiently translatable into processes of data acquisition and data analysis. What may present itself as problematic on this level could – as I would like to propose – in the field of education be counterbalanced with the help of human rights education. In this paper I would like to make this normative orientation plausible by firstly confronting it with the way didactics for the most part deals – up to today – with processes of digitalization. Having a basic anthropological starting point, human rights education helps illuminating the shifts in the human condition caused by digitalization and can, at the same time, intervene with its widely accepted norms. I will then illustrate this with the example of politics and by doing so also further answer the question why these shifts are of significant importance for setting up alternative digital infrastructures like an open and free search index.

THE SHORTCOMINGS OF DIDACTICS AND HUMAN RIGHTS EDUCATION AS A COUNTERWEIGHT

In textbooks for social studies used at German schools pupils are more or less left with their preconceptions of what digitalization means. Without clarifying basic notions, it’s almost inevitable for the textbooks to deal with the topic on a mere superficial level. In many cases this means establishing a dichotomy of dangers and possibilities of the digitalization and then attribute certain phenomena to either the chances or the risks – with a clear focus on the latter [6]. Fundamental changes beyond this ‘danger prevention’ are almost entirely neglected. Instead, the focus of the textbooks lies on strengthening media competency, meaning first and foremost to convey to pupils to use digital technology (including search engines) in an appropriate manner. This goal resonates with positions from cultural and educational politics in Germany (as well as from the European Union). For example, the “Digital Competence Framework for Educators” (DigCompEdu), developed by a research centre of the European Commission, aims almost exclusively for a self-activating and efficient usage of digital devices [7]. The same is true for a strategic paper published by the German “Conference of Ministers for Education” – titled “Competences in a digital World” [8]. The paper was updated in 2021; however, its focus on media competency remained.

The fact that a usage-oriented perspective on digitalization has its shortcomings was pointed out quite frequently. Werner Friedrichs, for example, remarked that understanding new technology merely as a tool for acquiring information is not sufficient. Instead, it has to be acknowledged

how technology interweaves in a reciprocal way with human life [9]. Similarly, Benjamin Jörissen and Lisa Unterberg argue for a perspective beyond media competency in order to grasp the profound and complex transformation processes of digitalization bring about [10]. A prominent and often used concept not so much to counter but to complement media competency (which stays undoubtedly important) is Felix Stalder’s notion of digitality (German: Digitalität). Stalder describes processes of digitalization as a deeply rooted cultural change which influences the constitution of social meaning, making it impossible to differentiate between the spheres of the analogue and the digital [11]. The assumption that there is a constant interdependency between technology on the one hand and humans on the other hand provides Stalder’s approach with a historical perspective – asking on which societal and cultural phenomena digitalization had built on – as well as it renders digital processes as open for human influence and intervention.

Stalder identifies three main characteristics of digitality – referentiality, new kinds of communities and algorithmicity. While referentiality deals with the increase of information and the way it loosens existing societal bonds, but establishing new ones at the same time, the notion of algorithmicity grasps the assistance of technology to help humans navigate the myriads of new information. Today, a considerable fraction of decision-making is already handed over to algorithms. The unprecedented possibilities of data acquisition and its algorithmic analysis can lead to a life curated by technology, promising humans an existence in comfort and security. The main objective of many companies in this sector is to make search engines obsolete altogether by knowing the needs of the people before they become conscious to themselves. In order to achieve that as much of cultural and social praxis as possible has to be dissolved into data. Relying solely on statistical predictability and patterns when dealing with culture and society can be conceptualised as a rigid regime of control [12]. Within such a regime the future is nothing more than a foreseeable and prolonged version of the present. A merely calculative approach toward reality implies the risk of people adapting with their perception and behaviour to such an approach – resulting in a world in which only those phenomena are visible and considered important which can be represented and measured by data. It would be a world to Peter Thiel’s liking because matters of freedom and self-determination would be left to technology without any human ‘contamination’. (It would be a world, for instance, in which machine learning is mainly advancing with the results of previous machine learning.) In short, the real danger lying within algorithmicity is not that technical instructions or machine learning becomes so ‘intelligent’ that it can outsmart humans but that humans behave more and more like the technology they invented.

This potential problem could be described in more detail with long-established notions like ‘alienation’ or ‘reification’. What thinkers of the past labelled, for instance, the ‘one-dimensional man’ (Herbert Marcuse) or a merely ‘instrumental reason’ (Max Horkheimer) was based on

analyses of economic structures or paradigms prevalent within academia (e. g. to give preference to quantitative methods). The alienation brought forth by technology was and still is inseparably intertwined with these structures – a relation which has, quite surprisingly, for present conditions not been extensively researched so far. Presumably, such research will offer explanations why people actively participate in establishing a regime which restricts their own freedom [13]. And the fact that freedom itself – distorted in a certain way – can become an instrument of power remains true even when the economic logic behind digital infrastructures in general and web search in particular has been restricted or even eliminated. There is no getting around the fact that selection is inevitable in this context – decisions need to be made what elements of society and culture to make visible, and what should remain invisible. And these decisions should not be left, as I argued for above, solely to technology. Within liberal societies they need to be subject to democratic processes and open debate – which, by the way, also means that drawing a clear-cut picture of a desirable future would be deceiving from the start.

Understanding reality as being open for humans to structure and shape it, is a core principle of human rights education. And the goal to strengthen solidarity and freedom among people in the present [14] is not achievable without taking the interwoven relation between technology and human beings into account. If this relation is neglected, one neither meets the standards of digitalization nor those of human rights education. Both are in need, so to speak, to be liquified; meaning that they should not be considered as static entities but as something characterized by processes and constant change [15]. Only such an approach prevents from dealing with digitalization in a merely superficial manner (which didactics is, as outlined above, often guilty of) and, furthermore, it prevents human rights to be nothing more than constantly repeated incantations for a better future. Instead, human rights education aspires to bring about cultural transformations [16] – against the backdrop of problematic developments within the ‘culture of digitality’. Avoiding the chimera of a total controllability and predictability of human life can be achieved by relying on the ‘utopian surplus’ [17] of human rights [18].

In order to do that education needs to rely heavily on interdisciplinarity; it has to aim at what Wolfgang Klafki named – as early as in the 1980s – an interconnected thinking [19]. Such an approach is able to illuminate phenomena in their complexity. Furthermore, education has to aim for a non-affirmative self-determination – which is a kind of self-determination that is critical toward its own conditions and, thus, opens the process of education towards goals which have to be determined during this very process [20]. It is exactly this kind of self-determination which is also crucial for the development of digital infrastructures which can be considered to be free in a non-instrumental way.

POLITICS AS AN EXAMPLE

It is not merely, for example, our privacy that is violated by large tech-companies, but the entire grammar of social

interactions is changing as well as of experiencing the world and perceiving each other. This is per se not something that calls for a lament because the *conditio humana* is ever-changing. But it definitely needs to be criticised to the extent of problematic developments becoming visible against the backdrop of democracy and human rights. It’s crucial to understand that even when there may be, one day, total self-determination in practice within the digital sphere there can nevertheless be questionable aspects present at the same time.

This interdependency and reciprocal influence between digital and analogue sphere (a differentiation which cannot be maintained, as outlined above, but is nevertheless helpful for purposes of clarification) can be illustrated with politics: Not lively debate but quantification, simulation and surveying constitute more and more the core of politics – which is a gradual process going on for a couple of decades now; consequently, technocrats take control by “administering pre-defined necessities and constellations which are [allegedly; MT] without any alternatives” [21]. These increasingly technocratic processes eliminate what Jürgen Habermas (among others) calls ‘reasoning’ (German: *Räsonnement*) and ‘deliberation’ – both elements which constitute an open debate characterized by the exchange of arguments and the aim to achieve a consensus. Back in the early 1960s Habermas identified political parties, associations and unions as key players in disengaging people from deliberation. The public is primarily needed for the acclimation of decisions that were already made [22]. Today it has additionally be reckoned with the omnipresence of surveying and the infrastructure of the digital sphere which both rely on the mere presentation of private opinions instead of helping to form political opinions. (Considering the latter this is especially true for social media.) What is left out here is the very process of deliberation. As Hartmut Rosa just recently put it concisely, aggregated private opinions are not be confused with deliberation [23]. Especially the possibilities of Big Data enforce the illusion that the will of the people is not something that is constituted by debates but instead something that is accurately measurable. Again, the issue at hand cannot be found on a superficial level – which would mean in this case that big tech-companies restrict the freedom of opinion in an active manner. Instead, it has to be addressed that what we consider to be an opinion changes in a way that contradicts the notion of ‘opinion’ itself by aligning it to the infrastructures of the digital sphere.

One potential issue for the future will be that an open search index exists side to side with ongoing rationalities of quantification, short-sided rationality and reification. These rivalling ‘logics’ will constantly challenge the search index and make it hard for its openness and freedom to prevail. A structurally similar problem presents itself in setting up the index: The network to develop and continuously evaluating, monitoring and moderating the index may not be established from scratch but vast areas of the public sphere are – due to its current state – bound to remain alien to the network’s core principles. This state of the public sphere in question is characterized by giving priority to

economic measures, by individualization, (self-)dramatization and emotionalizing – all traits with a tendency to contradict or lead astray democratic values. Again, with the help of Habermas’ “Structural Transformation of the public Sphere” it’s possible to realize that these processes are not something new. Problems to engage people in political debate and to form a public sphere which is able to gain the attention of societal majorities (which is according to Habermas key for a democracy to function) were also present during the emergence of television in the mid-20th century.

Nevertheless, there has been – as Habermas calls it – a “centripetal pull” [24] of what can be called classic mass media. In contrast to that, the public sphere of the internet is fragmented from the start. Following Felix Stalder – as outlined in the introduction – this can be on the one hand described as a strength in that debates are opened for a more diverse chorus of voices. But on the other hand, there are undoubtedly centrifugal forces at work which may lead (or perhaps already have been led) to a society unable to determine which topics are worthy of discussion. While these ruptures take place the ‘old’ mass media – e. g. newspapers, radio, television – is more and more feeling the pressure to adapt to the new regime which reinforces the problems even further [25]. The results are what Habermas labels as “semi-public spheres” [26] – odd mixtures of private and public spheres. This development, again, points into the direction of a fundamental change: For example, it is not fake news themselves – or even their increasing appearance – that is problematic for the political public sphere but the fact that this very sphere is distorted in a way which makes it increasingly difficult to identify fake news as such [27]. So, the underlying issue being that our understanding of truth and reality slowly but steadily shifts means that simply identifying lies in the form of fake news falls short to the backdrop of the problem at hand.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, even setting up the most open and transparent digital infrastructure should not overshadow the fact that there are (and ever will be) qualities of life and human interaction [28] which cannot be adequately captured by data and its statistical interpretation. This aspect can be – as illustrated in this paper – made visible in the field of education with the help of human rights education. Being critical in such a fundamental way may prevent an overarching lock-in-effect which nowadays adds up to existing economical lock-in-effects [29]. With an open and free search index and digital self-determination in place people might as well opt for their lives being curated by technology – possibly for the very reason that it is a technology they now have control over. But by doing so they have to be aware that certain qualities of their humanness, of what makes them unique and distinctive simply fall short.

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